

Date of publication: April 18, 2022

DOI: [10.52270/26585561_2022_14_16_28](https://doi.org/10.52270/26585561_2022_14_16_28)

Historical Sciences

DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE IN MODERN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article discusses the development of sports in modern Russia among young people. It is shown that urgent development and implementation of a state program aimed at countering the emerging trend of deterioration in the health of the population is currently needed. The new measures should provide for a whole range of social, medical, preventive, organizational and economic tasks. In order to attract young people to the formation of their own health, a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to form a positive public opinion about physical culture and sports at the state level. This is really important because physical culture and sports are a special kind of creative activity that allows you to form a healthy lifestyle of the population, in particular students.

Keywords: sports, youth, society, state, university.

I. INTRODUCTION

Russian sport as a sphere of activity, lifestyle, social institution with its structural and functional characteristics, as an agent of socialization is in a state of transformation.

The inconsistency of the state's policy towards sports leads to the fact that some sports flourish, receive solid financial and material assistance, while others exist in survival mode or disappear unnoticed. This is accompanied, on the one hand, by the destruction of the management structure of mass sports, the removal of sports from the priority attitudes of the population at the level of mass consciousness, which results in a catastrophic decline in the physical and mental health of people, in particular young people.

On the other hand, it should be recognized that young people receive freedom of self-determination as a necessary condition for fruitful activity, self-affirmation of each young person and the entire socio-demographic group. One of these freedoms is the possibility of self-realization of young people in physical culture and sports, as well as the expansion of ideas about their wellness opportunities.

II. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

For modern Russia, the problem of youth health and its relationship with physical culture and sports is put forward among the priorities of social and social development. This determines the relevance of its theoretical and practical development, the need to deploy appropriate scientific research and the development of methodological and organizational approaches.

In the works of such Russian scientists as S.A. Berdyshev, G.L. Bilich, E.N. Weiner, V.I. Garbuzov, V.I. Dubrovsky, N.V. Pankratiev, V.F. Popov, D. Chopra, B.N. Chumakov, medical aspects of the study of health problems prevail, while social ones are put on the back burner.

A healthy lifestyle was studied by Yu.Yu. Andreev Yu.Yu., N.M. Amosov, I.I. Brekhman, V.I. Belov, S.P. Letunov, Yu.P. Lisitsin, V.N. Nikolaev, V.G. Chaitsev, G. Shelton, their research interest is mainly focused on the problems of recovery, rehabilitation, restoration of already lost or reduced health.

The scientific research of E.H. Zakharov, Yu.I. Evseev, E.P. Ilyin, V.I. Kozhin, L.I. Lubysheva and others reflected the relationship of human health and a healthy lifestyle with physical culture and sports. Physical culture and sports in Russia are in a state of social transformation, institutional changes, they are distinguished by the trajectory of spontaneous development and periphery in the life of the main population groups.

Our research allowed us to consider the problems of the impact of sports and physical culture on the health of modern Russian youth and get answers to the questions posed. In the course of the work carried out, the hypothesis was confirmed that in the modern socio-economic and political conditions in which modern Russia is located, the factors of realizing the humanistic potential of physical culture and sports in the formation of a healthy lifestyle are not sufficiently in demand, the values of health, healthy lifestyle, physical culture and sports are not significant in the youth environment.

They are inferior to the values of education and professional career. Young people treat physical culture and sports in a consumer way. The role of physical culture and sports as factors in the formation of a healthy lifestyle of young people is undoubtedly very significant.

However, the data of our own sociological research, expert assessment of other sociological surveys and statistical data allow us to conclude that the value of physical culture and sports in the assessments of Russian youth is characterized by their decline as factors in the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

At the same time, the competition of new types of achievable activities is increasing. Pragmatism in the assessment of physical culture and sports reflects the aspirations of young people to market values, success and independence.

As a result of large-scale changes in the course of reforms, there have been value shifts in the minds of Russian youth. As the conducted sociological analysis shows, modern young people are mainly focused on consumer values or suffer from a complex of "material underconsumption", exclude sports as "not bringing a lot of pleasure and associated with certain moral prohibitions."

According to the results of sociological research, sport turned out to be a significant factor, not to mention its health aspects, only for 25% of respondents, 45% of respondents estimated this value at 4-5 points, 20% - 2-3 points. The purchase of sports equipment, sportswear and shoes, payment for classes in sports and wellness sections takes 10-12 places in the budget of young Russians on a par with the theater, museums, classical music concerts.

As shown in the article, in modern society, sports and physical culture perform the functions of agents of forming a healthy lifestyle, allowing an individual to work out social roles in the process of sports activity and gain the social experience he needs. Sport and physical culture combine the social and biological in a person, serve as an effective mechanism for preserving social, social and individual health.

The effectiveness of the formation of a healthy lifestyle and, ultimately, the development of society itself is decisively influenced by the increase in the involvement of individuals in sports and physical culture, therefore, one of the priority tasks facing society is the development of mass children's and youth sports and physical culture. Despite the fact that many factors affecting the popularity of sports in society are subjective, nevertheless, as the experience of a number of countries of the world shows, mass involvement of the population in sports is possible. Modern society is not able to fully solve the problem of the mass nature of the physical culture and sports movement without the support of the state. Therefore, the problems of the development of sports and physical culture, as a rule, find their solution at the highest state level. In general, the spread of mass sports is a priority task of the state in all developed societies of the world.

The return to the concept of "wellness" and "preventive" sports is associated with the scale of "disability" of Russian youth, the growth of crime, drug addiction, substance abuse, suicide. When society is unable to pay for the "recovery" of the younger generation, the role of the state is indisputable. The powerful entertainment industry (music, beer), the threat of underfunding of youth sports (6% in Russia versus 30% in Finland), distrust of young people in official institutions and the compulsion of sports socialization hinder the implementation of the tasks set.

The analysis of the value priorities of young people indicates the movement of sports into the category of "floating values" included in "consumption practices" or "safe life". Sport has lost its traditional integrative significance and its achievement potential is not appreciated. Today it is necessary to develop a unified strategy of actions of various ministries, departments, public organizations, scientists and specialists based on building up health reserves, on the protection and reproduction of a healthy nation. This strategy should be aimed at creating the most favorable conditions for the recovery of Russian youth.

III. CONCLUSION

The search for solutions to the problems that have arisen leads to the conclusion that it is necessary to urgently develop and implement a state program designed to promote a healthy lifestyle, improve the quality and level of health and provide for a whole range of social, medical, preventive, organizational and economic measures.

Currently, in order to attract young people to the formation of their own health, as the most important condition for human self-realization in all spheres of activity, strengthening the health and preventive aspects of physical culture and sports, it is necessary at the state level to develop attempts to create a positive public opinion about physical culture and sports, the "fashion" of sports and a healthy lifestyle, about specialists and professionals in this field, their successes and achievements.

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РАЗВИТИЕ СПОРТА В МОЛОДЁЖНОЙ СРЕДЕ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается развитие спорта в современной России в молодёжной среде. Показано, что в настоящее время необходима срочная разработка и реализация государственной программы, направленной на противодействие наметившейся тенденции ухудшения здоровья населения. Новые меры должны предусматривать решение всего комплекса социальных, медицинских, профилактических, организационно-хозяйственных задач. Для привлечения молодежи к формированию собственного здоровья, здорового образа жизни необходимо формирование положительного общественного мнения о физической культуре и спорте на государственном уровне. Это действительно важно, поскольку физическая культура и спорт являются особым видом творческой деятельности, позволяющим формировать здоровый образ жизни населения, в частности студенческой молодежи.

Ключевые слова: спорт, молодежь, общество, государство, вуз.

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